

Enhanced Dynamic Response of Grid-Connected PV Systems Using Adaptive Fuzzy Logic Control

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Abstract

In recent years, the integration of renewable energy sources has been growing steadily, with the goal of decreasing dependence on fossil fuels for electricity generation. Photovoltaic systems are favored in both remote and urban areas with adequate sunlight. The use of Photovoltaic (PV) is on the rise due to increasing fuel prices and technological advancements that have significantly lowered manufacturing costs. This paper introduces a comprehensive controller design for single-phase, single-stage grid-connected PV systems. The performance of the proposed controller is evaluated through both simulation and experimental methods. A single-phase H-bridge inverter is used to connect the system to the grid, with the inverter control scheme consisting of two primary loops: DC-link voltage (DLV) and current control. The DLV control employs a PI controller, a fuzzy logic controller (FLC), and an adaptive fuzzy logic controller (AFLC) to improve the dynamic response of the DLV without the need for a feed-forward signal from the DC side, reducing the number of sensors required for supplying DC loads in rectifying mode. The controller's performance is assessed under both inverting and rectifying modes. Simulation and experimental results demonstrate that the AFLC outperforms the FLC and PI controller in terms of settling time and steady-state error. Additionally, the power injected into the utility grid is managed by the current control loop in the synchronous (DQ) reference frame, with a PI controller used to regulate the grid current. The results indicate that the injected current meets the general requirements for distributed generators.

Keywords: *Grid connected, Photovoltaic, Fuzzy Logic control, adaptive fuzzy logic controller, dynamic response.*

Introduction

The integration of renewable energy systems (RES) into modern power grids is a cornerstone for achieving global energy sustainability and addressing climate change challenges [1,2]. RESs, such as solar, wind, and hydropower, offer a clean and inexhaustible supply of energy, significantly reducing greenhouse gas emissions compared to fossil fuels. Additionally, the declining costs of renewable technologies, driven by advancements in materials, manufacturing processes, and economies of scale, have made these systems increasingly competitive with conventional energy sources [3].

Grid-connected inverters (GCI) play a pivotal role in the integration of renewable energy systems, acting as the interface between renewable energy generation units and the utility grid. These devices are essential for converting DC electricity, produced by solar photovoltaic (PV) panels or other RES, into AC that is compatible with grid standards [3]. In addition to power conversion, modern GCI are equipped with advanced functionalities such as voltage and frequency regulation, reactive power support, and fault ride-through capabilities, which are critical for maintaining grid stability in the face of fluctuating renewable energy inputs. The adoption of GCI also supports distributed generation and decentralized energy models, allowing consumers to become "prosumers" who can both consume and supply electricity. As the penetration of renewable energy systems continues to grow, the development and deployment of robust, efficient, and intelligent GCI will remain indispensable for achieving a resilient and sustainable energy future [4,5].

The demand for single-phase inverters is growing as the market for small-scale renewable energy systems expands. Grid-connected PV systems require advanced DLV and current controllers to mitigate second harmonic ripples and to ensure the injection of high-quality current into the grid. The control loops of grid-connected inverters commonly comprise the Phase-Locked Loop (PLL), the Pulse Width Modulation (PWM) block, the Current Control (CC) loop, and the DLV Control (DLVC) loop, each playing a crucial role in maintaining stable and efficient operation [4,5]. The PLL is pivotal for synchronizing the inverter with the grid by accurately tracking the grid voltage angle, ensuring a consistent phase relationship between the inverter current and the grid voltage. This synchronization is essential for reliable power exchange with the grid. The PWM block translates control signals generated by the CC loop into precise switching signals for the inverter. By modulating the inverter switches accurately, the PWM enables the delivery of desired current and voltage waveforms to the grid or load. The CC loop is responsible for regulating the inverter output current to match the reference signals provided by the DLVC loop. It ensures that the injected active and reactive power aligns with desired values while maintaining current waveforms within permissible limits. The DLVC loop, as the outermost control layer, regulates the DC-link voltage to its reference value, balancing the power supplied by the DC source, such as a photovoltaic array, with the power delivered to the grid or load. This hierarchy of control loops ensures robust synchronization, power quality, and stability even under dynamic operating conditions.

On this topic, numerous research studies have been published. Ref. [6] introduced a PI-based closed-loop control optimized using the chicken swarm algorithm, ensuring a stable and consistent output from the converter. The authors in [7] presented a Takagi-Sugeno-Kang fuzzy controller-based inverter designed for a single-stage grid-tied PV system, which also functions as an MPPT converter for the PV system. Ref. [8] presented a robust control strategy for single-phase PV grid-tied inverters, featuring a hybrid phase-locked loop for grid synchronization, an integral sliding mode current controller for accurate power injection, and sliding mode voltage control for precise DC-link voltage tracking. The authors of [9] analyzed the performance of a two-stage single-phase inverter for grid-connected PV systems using MATLAB simulations, incorporating a maximum power point tracking (MPPT) technique to enhance system efficiency. In [10], the authors proposed a novel sensorless DLV control method for a two-stage three-phase

grid-connected PV system, designed to generate an active reference current for PV power generation. This method eliminates the need for an outer control loop, offering a new model for DLVC that produces an active reference current. The study in [11] introduced two techniques for controlling DLV: a Fuzzy Logic-Based PI Controller and a Fuzzy Logic-Based Sliding Mode Controller. Additionally, for a single-phase, two-stage, transformerless grid-connected PV inverter, a Proportional Resonant Controller with a Resonant Harmonic Compensator was proposed as the current controller. A 3 kW single-phase, two-stage transformerless grid-connected PV system was modeled using MATLAB/Simulink, and a comparative analysis was conducted between the proposed controllers and a conventional PI controller. Meanwhile, the authors of [12] employed a composite incremental conductance method as the MPPT strategy to manage the boost converter in a two-stage three-phase grid-connected solar PV system. They ALSO introduced an adaptive DLVC for regulating the GCI and developed an approximate linear model with feed-forward compensation for the DLV control loop, which was subsequently analyzed.

This paper presents a detailed design of the control system for a single-phase GCI. The dynamic modeling of the inverter's operation in the synchronous reference frame is also discussed. The design of the proposed inverter side controller is outlined, while details of the FLC and AFLC are developed. The simulation results are discussed, followed by the experimental results which included in the section of results and discussions. Finally, the conclusions are presented.

Dynamic model of the inverter side in DQ-frame

DQ transformation is widely used in three-phase systems, where the system is converted into a two-phase stationary coordinate system (α and β) using the Clarke transformation matrix. The stationary α and β variables are then mapped to a DQ frame through the Park transformation [13]. In this DQ frame, the components rotate at the same angular frequency as the converter's fundamental frequency, converting all time-varying parameters into DC, time-invariant parameters. This conversion simplifies the design and analysis of the controller since DC components are easier to manage.

Converting to the synchronous frame requires at least two independent phases, but only one phase is present in a single-phase system. To enable the transformation from a stationary to a rotating frame, a second, imaginary phase must be generated. Various methods exist for obtaining this imaginary phase [14–17]. In this work, the imaginary phase is created by introducing a 90° phase shift relative to the real phase, as described below:

At unity power factor, let the utility grid voltage (v_g) and the grid current (i_g) be:

$$\begin{aligned} v_g &= v_m \sin(\omega t) \\ i_g &= i_m \sin(\omega t) \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

By shifting Equation (1) by 90° , the imaginary (β) component is:

$$\begin{aligned} v_{\beta} &= v_{g_{imag}} = v_m \sin(\omega t - 90) = -v_m \cos(\omega t) \\ i_{\beta} &= i_{g_{imag}} = i_m \sin(\omega t - 90) = -i_m \cos(\omega t) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

In the following equations, subscripts α and β represent the signal in α β -frame; and subscripts d and q in the DQ - frame. Based on the system in Fig.1, the average model of the VSI AC side can be termed as:

$$L_s \frac{d i_g}{dt} + r_s i_g = m v_{dc} - v_g \quad (3)$$

Where v_{dc} , L_s , r_s and m represent DLV, the inductance of AC side filter, the resistance of the AC side filter and the modulation index, respectively. A single-phase inverter average model in the DQ-frame is developed by splitting the inverter model into two ‘virtual’ circuits (α and β circuits). The α - β model of the system is

$$L_s \frac{d}{dt} \begin{pmatrix} i_{\alpha} \\ i_{\beta} \end{pmatrix} + r_s \begin{pmatrix} i_{\alpha} \\ i_{\beta} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} m_{\alpha} v_{dc} \\ m_{\beta} v_{dc} \end{pmatrix} - \begin{pmatrix} v_{g\alpha} \\ v_{g\beta} \end{pmatrix} \quad (4)$$

Further, the system in (1)-(4) is converted in to the synchronous frame by applying the transformation matrix (T) and equals $\begin{pmatrix} \sin \theta & -\cos \theta \\ \cos \theta & \sin \theta \end{pmatrix}$ [18]. The behavior of the AC-side variables represented in the DQ reference frame can be outlined as follows [18–20]:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d i_{gd}}{dt} &= L_s \omega_o i_{gq} - r_s i_{gd} + v_{td} - v_{gd} \\ \frac{d i_{gq}}{dt} &= -L_s \omega_o i_{gd} - r_s i_{gq} + v_{tq} - v_{gq} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Where $\begin{pmatrix} v_{td} \\ v_{tq} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} m_d v_{dc} \\ m_q v_{dc} \end{pmatrix}$

The active and reactive powers injected into the grid are given as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} P_g \\ Q_g \end{bmatrix} = \frac{1}{2} \begin{bmatrix} v_{gd} & v_{gq} \\ v_{gq} & -v_{gd} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} i_{gd} \\ i_{gq} \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

The controller design of single- phase GCI

Figure 1 illustrates the architecture of the inverter-side controller, showcasing its organized structure comprising four interconnected control loops. These loops are integral to ensuring efficient and stable operation of the inverter under varying conditions. The control loops include the PLL, the PWM block, the CC loop, and the DLVC.

The proposed controller’s parameters are systematically designed to achieve optimal performance in terms of stability, dynamic response, and robustness. Each loop is tuned to complement the others, enabling precise control of the inverter’s operation while meeting performance requirements across various operating scenarios. The following sections detail the methodology used to design the control parameters for each loop.

Figure 1. Proposed inverter side controller.

Grid synchronization

Accurate detection of the grid angle at the PCC is a critical requirement for achieving synchronization with the utility grid. This synchronization ensures proper alignment of the inverter's output current with the grid voltage, which is essential for stable and efficient power exchange.

To achieve this, a PLL algorithm is employed, as it is well-suited for precise and rapid estimation of the grid angle. The PLL continuously monitors the grid voltage waveform and adjusts its internal phase to match the grid angle accurately. This capability enables the inverter to maintain a synchronized phase relationship with the grid, regardless of variations in grid conditions, such as frequency fluctuations or voltage disturbances.

The effectiveness of the PLL lies in its ability to adapt dynamically to grid changes while minimizing synchronization errors. Extensive research and prior studies [21,22] have validated the robustness and reliability of PLL-based methods for grid angle detection. These studies emphasize the importance of PLL tuning to ensure fast convergence to the actual grid angle without introducing instability or excessive delay.

By integrating the PLL into the control strategy, the inverter system achieves seamless grid synchronization, enabling it to operate efficiently under diverse operating conditions, including fault recovery, load changes, and transient disturbances. This synchronization also facilitates the accurate regulation of P_g and Q_g , contributing to the overall reliability and performance of the grid-connected system.

In this study, the stationary reference frame phase locked loop ($\alpha\beta$ PLL) is the chosen PLL approach. As shown in Figure 2, it is designed such as to make the difference ($\Delta\theta$) between grid angle (θ) and estimated PLL angle (θ_{pll}) to be zero.

Figure 2. Schematic diagram of $\alpha\beta$ PLL method.

The linear model between $\Delta\theta$ and $\Delta\omega$ is given by:

$$G_{pll}(s) = \frac{v_m}{s} \quad (7)$$

The transfer functions for the open-loop and closed-loop systems are provided in equations (8) and (9), respectively.

$$\ell_{pll}(s) = \frac{v_m(k_{pL}s + k_{iL})}{s^2} \quad (8)$$

$$C_{pll}(s) = \frac{v_m(k_{pL}s + k_{iL})}{s^2 + v_m k_{pL}s + v_m k_{iL}} \quad (9)$$

The mathematical model presented in Equation (9) represents a standard second-order system that includes a single real zero. Such a system is commonly characterized by its natural frequency and damping ratio, which play crucial roles in defining the dynamic response of the system.

In the context of the PLL design, these parameters—natural frequency (ω_{npll}) and damping ratio (ζ_{npll})—are carefully selected to achieve an optimal balance between responsiveness and stability. The natural frequency determines the speed at which the PLL can track changes in the grid angle, while the damping ratio ensures that oscillations in the system response are minimized, providing a smooth convergence to the desired grid phase.

Based on the selected values of ω_{npll} and ζ_{npll} , the parameters of the PLL controller can be derived. These parameters are calculated to ensure that the closed-loop PLL system meets the desired performance criteria. The tuning process involves using the second-order system's transfer function to relate the PLL dynamics to its control gains, ensuring that the system adheres to its design specifications.

By properly tuning these parameters, the PLL achieves accurate and reliable synchronization with the grid under a wide range of operating conditions. This capability is essential for applications where precise grid angle detection is critical, such as grid-connected inverters, active power filters, and renewable energy systems. Further details of the parameter derivation process and their impact on PLL performance are discussed in subsequent sections.

$$k_{iL} = \frac{\omega_{npLL}^2}{v_m} \quad (10)$$

$$k_{pL} = \frac{2\xi_{pLL} \omega_{npLL}}{v_m} \quad (11)$$

Space Vector PWM (SVPWM)

The SVPWM for a single-phase VSI operates on principles similar to those used in three-phase systems. However, the implementation in single-phase inverters is significantly simpler due to reduced dimensional complexity.

The SVPWM technique for single-phase inverters can be summarized in the following steps, providing an efficient approach for generating high-quality output waveforms with minimal harmonic distortion [23,24]:

Step 1: Determine the reference signal (v_{ref})

The reference voltage is obtained by transforming the DQ components to phase signals. The reference signal and its angle are calculated as:

The reference voltage is obtained by transforming the DQ components to phase signals. The reference signal and its angle are calculated as:

$$v_{tref} = v_{t\alpha} = v_{tm} \sin(\omega t) \quad (12)$$

$$v_{t\alpha} > 0 \Rightarrow 0 < \omega t \leq \pi \quad (13)$$

$$v_{t\alpha} \geq 0 \Rightarrow \pi < \omega t \leq 2\pi$$

Step 2: Identify the sector in which the voltage vector is located and calculate the corresponding time intervals (T1, T2 and T0)

The sector determines the spatial region of the voltage vector within the modulation scheme, guiding the selection of appropriate switching states. The time intervals T_1 and T_2 represent the durations for which the active vectors are applied to approximate the reference voltage. T_0 corresponds to the zero vector duration, used to balance the switching sequence and maintain proper modulation. This step is critical for ensuring accurate representation of the desired output voltage and achieving a smooth and efficient modulation process.

As illustrated in Figure 3, each switching state can be represented by a corresponding space vector. The choice of V_1 and V_2 , is determined by the phase angle (ωt) of the reference voltage.

- When $0 < \omega t \leq \pi$, the reference voltage increases from zero to v_{dc} , and vector V_1 is selected. This indicates that the reference voltage resides in Sector I.
- Conversely, when $\pi \leq \omega t < 2\pi$ is utilized, signifying that the reference voltage is now in Sector II.

This approach ensures that the reference voltage is accurately approximated by the appropriate active vectors within the respective sectors, enabling smooth and efficient modulation.

Figure 3. The basic of space vectors of single phase H-bridge inverter.

The time intervals for each state are determined based on the following conditions:

- Condition 1: (sector I):

Each vector's time duration is calculated as follows:

$$T_1 = \frac{V_m}{V_{dc}} T_s \sin \omega t = m T_s \sin \omega t \quad (14)$$

$$T_2 = 0 \quad (15)$$

$$T_{0,3} = T_s - T_1 \quad (16)$$

Where T_1 , T_2 and T_0 represent the time durations associated with the switching states corresponding to V_1 , V_2 , and $V_{0,3}$, respectively.

- Condition 2: (sector II):

The active and null vectors time durations are given as:

$$T_2 = \left| \frac{V_m}{V_{dc}} T_s \sin \omega t \right| = |m T_s \sin \omega t| \quad (17)$$

$$T_1 = 0 \quad (18)$$

$$T_{0,3} = T_s - T_2 \quad (19)$$

Step 3: Determine the switching pattern

As explained in [25], an optimal switching pattern with reduced switching actions can be achieved by carefully selecting the null vectors. This approach is equally applicable to single-phase Voltage Source Inverters (VSI), and the chosen pattern is shown in Figure 4.

Current controller design

P_g and Q_g injected into or absorbed from the grid is regulated in the DQ-frame through the inverter's output current, as described in Equation (6). In this frame, the active power is represented by the component i_{gd} , while the reactive power is controlled by i_{gq} . When the reactive power component v_q is set to zero, the coupling terms in Equation (6) become zero, simplifying the system. Under these conditions, the reference signals i_{gdref} and i_{gqref} are directly responsible for determining the injected active and reactive powers, respectively.

The primary objective of the current regulator is to ensure that the inverter output current accurately tracks the reference signals i_{gdref} and i_{gqref} . Achieving this requires the current regulator to exhibit a rapid and stable dynamic response to fluctuations in the reference signals. By maintaining this tracking accuracy, the inverter can control the bidirectional power flow between the grid and the inverter. This process allows the system to inject or absorb the required P_g and Q_g , meeting the demands of the grid under various operating conditions.

Thus, the current regulator plays a crucial role in ensuring that the power flow remains within the desired parameters, facilitating efficient energy transfer and maintaining grid stability. The ability of the current regulator to quickly respond to changes in the reference signals is essential for achieving the required power flows while minimizing oscillations and maintaining system performance.

Figure 4. Switching scheme and ON-OFF status for single phase full bridge power switches

Figure 5 shows the CC loop in DQ -frame. The transfer function between the controller action (u_{dq}) and (i_{dq}) is first order as follows:

$$G_i(s) = \frac{i_{gdq}}{u_{dq}} = \frac{1/L_s}{s + r_s/L_s} \tag{20}$$

As all the control signals are DC quantities in steady state, a simple PI-compensator can be applied to track the set points with a small steady state error. The parameters of PI- controller are selected that the controller cancel the slowdown pole and the CC loop, which is the inner loop of the whole system, has faster response. However, it should be sufficiently large so that its reciprocal, representing the closed-loop system's

bandwidth (ω_{ii}), is significantly lower than the switching frequency—typically by a factor of ten or more. K_{pi} and k_{ii} are calculated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} k_{pi} &= \omega_{ii} L_s \\ k_{ii} &= \frac{k_{pi} R_s}{L_s} \end{aligned} \tag{21}$$

Figure 5. Block diagram of CC loop.

DLV controller design

Maintaining the power balance between the output AC power to the utility (p_v) and the input power (p_{dc}) from PV arrays or DC-to-DC converters requires DLV management. The relation between v_{dc} and i_{gdref} is obtained as follows:

The power balance is given as:

$$p_{dc} - p_{loss} - v_{dc} C_{dc} \frac{dv_{dc}}{dt} = p_{inv_{dc}} = p_t = \frac{v_{td} i_{gd}}{2} \tag{22}$$

Assuming unity power factor and substituting equation (5) in equation (22) and, we deduce [26]:

$$\begin{aligned} p_{dc} - p_{loss} - v_{dc} C_{dc} \frac{dv_{dc}}{dt} &= \frac{i_{gd}}{2} \left[i_{gd} v_{gd} + i_{gd} L_s \frac{di_{gd}}{dt} + r_s i_{gd}^2 \right] \\ \frac{L_s}{K_{pi}} i_{gd} + i_{gd} &= i_{gdref} \end{aligned} \tag{23}$$

Where v_{dc} is the state variable, p_{dc} and p_{loss} are the disturbance inputs. Equation (23) indicates that under transient and steady state conditions, the disturbance input (p_{dc}) impacts on v_{dc} response.

The controller requirement could be achieved using a PI-controller, however the dynamic response of v_{dc} degrades without augmenting p_{dc} as the feed forward signal, as shown in figure 6 [27]. To design PI-controller, the designing procedure is straightforward: the linear model between v_{dc} and i_{gdref} is obtained first since the DLV is the outer loop of the inner current loop, then an appropriate compensator is employed to obtain the controller requirements. The linearized model between v_{dc} and i_{gdref} is obtained as follows:

$$G_v(s) = \frac{\tilde{v}_{dc}}{i_{gd}} = -k_{sys} \frac{(T_z s + 1)}{s} \tag{24}$$

Where $k_{sys} = \frac{2r_s i_{gdo} + V_{gdo}}{2C_{dc} V_{dco}}$, $T_z = \frac{L_s i_{gdo}}{2r_s i_{gdo} + V_{gdo}}$ and the symbol (\sim) indicates small signal perturbations. The

transfer function from \tilde{v}_{dc} to \tilde{i}_{igdref} is given by:

$$\frac{\tilde{v}_{dc}}{\tilde{i}_{igdref}} = -k_{sys} \frac{(T_z s + 1)}{s \left(\frac{L_s}{k_{pi}} s + 1 \right)} \tag{25}$$

Figure 6. Control block diagram of DLV loop.

In figure 7, a negative sign is incorporated into the controller to offset the negative sign present in $G_v(s)$. The bandwidth of DC-voltage loop (ω_v) is selected lower than ω_i to nullify the phase delay of $G_i(s)$. The parameters of PI-controller can be obtained as follows:

The open loop transfer function is given by:

$$l_v(s) = k_{iv} k_{sys} \frac{(T_c s + 1)(T_z s + 1)}{s^2} \tag{26}$$

Where T_c equals (k_{iv} / k_{pv}) . k_{iv} and k_{pv} are the integrator and proportional gains of DLV PI-controller. The controller parameters are designed in order to have phase margin of 45° and the bandwidth frequency of DC-link voltage loop is smaller than the current loop. k_{iv} and k_{pv} are calculated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} k_{iv} &= \frac{\omega_g^2}{k_{sys} \sqrt{(1 - T_c T_z \omega_g^2)^2 + (T_c + T_z)^2 \omega_g^2}} \\ k_{pv} &= T_c k_{iv} \\ T_c &= \frac{1 - \omega_g T_z}{\omega_g + T_z \omega_g^2} \end{aligned} \tag{27}$$

Where ω_g is the selected gain cross over frequency.

Figure 7. Block diagram of DLV loop using a PI-controller.

Design of FLC and AFLC

The following describes a method for implementing a PI-like FLC. In this approach, the fuzzy controller operates with two inputs: the error (e) and the change in error (Δe), and produces one output: the change in the control signal ($\Delta i_{g\text{dref}}$). The control signal ($i_{g\text{dref}}$, as shown in Figure 8) is produced by integrating the output of the fuzzy logic controller.

Each of the fuzzy variables—both the inputs and the output—are associated with three linguistic terms: negative (N), zero (Z), and positive (P). These terms are represented by triangular membership functions, as illustrated in Figure 9. The fuzzy controller's behavior is determined by the extent to which each input and output belongs to these linguistic categories.

To standardize the system, the parameters X_{max} and X_{min} define the maximum and minimum possible variations of the input and output signals. These values are selected based on the data obtained from simulations. The scaling factor $k=1/X_{\text{max}}$ is then applied to normalize the range of each fuzzy variable between -1 and +1, effectively mapping the actual signal range into a symmetric scale. This normalization step ensures consistency and prevents overflow or extreme values in the fuzzy system.

A symmetric fuzzy rule set, shown in Table 1, governs the decision-making process of the PI-like FLC. This rule set defines how the fuzzy system will respond to different combinations of error and error change, enabling the controller to adjust the control signal accordingly. By following these rules, the fuzzy controller can effectively regulate the system's output, providing smooth and adaptive control with respect to the desired performance criteria.

Figure 8. PI-like FLC.

Figure 9. Membership functions for inputs and outputs.

Table 1. Rules of FLC.

$e \backslash \Delta e$	N	Z	P
N	N	N	Z
Z	N	Z	P
P	Z	P	P

The center of gravity (COG) defuzzification method is utilized to convert the fuzzy output into a precise, crisp control value. This method involves calculating the weighted average of the centroids of the membership functions associated with the output variable. In this context, let θ_i denote the centroid of the i^{th} membership function corresponding to the output variable.

For a fuzzy controller with nine rules, the defuzzified output is determined by considering the centroids of the membership functions for each rule, weighted according to their firing strengths. The weighted average of these centroids is then computed to produce the final crisp control signal. This process allows the fuzzy controller to translate its fuzzy logic-based decisions into a real-world control action that can be applied to the system. The mathematical formulation for calculating the defuzzified output Δu can be expressed as:

$$\Delta u = \frac{\sum_1^9 \omega_i \theta_i}{\sum_1^9 \omega_i} = \underline{\theta}^T \tau \tag{28}$$

Where: $\tau_i = \frac{\omega_i}{\sum_1^m \omega_i}$, the strength of the i^{th} rule is ω_i .

Figure 10 illustrates the proposed method based on the AFLC and provides a detailed structure of how the AFLC operates. The diagram highlights the key components of the system, including the real-time adaptation of the centroids and the overall control architecture, which collectively contribute to the improved performance of the regulator. This adaptive approach ensures that the controller can continuously adjust its parameters for optimal system control, making it suitable for dynamic and varying operating conditions.

Figure 10. Suggested algorithm based on AFLC.

The adaptive fuzzy scheme can be presented as follows [28]:

Let the nonlinear system be expressed as shown in [28]:

$$\ddot{x} = f(\underline{x}) + bu \tag{29}$$

$$y = x \quad (30)$$

In this system, the state-variable vector is denoted by \underline{x} , and u represents the control signal. The control input u is selected in such a way that it effectively cancels out the system's nonlinearities, allowing the design of a controller based on linear control theory principles. One common approach for this is pole placement, a technique used to place the poles of the system at desired locations in the complex plane to achieve the desired dynamic behavior (such as stability, response time, and damping).

By choosing the control input u in this manner, the system can be treated as a linear system, simplifying the design of the controller. The design is based on mathematical techniques from linear control theory, enabling more predictable and manageable system performance.

The control law, which defines how the control input u is determined based on the state variables, is typically expressed in the following form:

$$u^* = \frac{1}{b} [-f(\underline{x}) + \ddot{y}_m + \underline{k}^T \underline{e}] \quad (31)$$

Let the tracking error is:

$$e = y_m - x, \quad \dot{e} = \dot{y}_m - \dot{x}, \quad \ddot{e} = \ddot{y}_m - \ddot{x} \quad (32)$$

Hence, the tracking error state vector, \underline{e} , can be selected as:

$$\underline{e} = [e \quad \dot{e}]^T \quad (33)$$

Where: the design vector, \underline{k} , is given by:

$$\underline{k}^T = [k_2 \quad k_1]$$

Substituting u^* for u from (31) to (29) leads to:

$$\ddot{x} = \ddot{y}_m + \underline{k}^T \underline{e} \quad (34)$$

Given the previously defined tracking error, \underline{e} , Equation (35) can be reformulated as:

$$\ddot{e} + \underline{k}^T \underline{e} = \ddot{e} + k_1 \dot{e} + k_2 e = 0 \quad (35)$$

The characteristic equation of error model equation (36) is given by:

$$S^2 + k_1 S + k_2 = 0 \quad (36)$$

The parameters k_1, \dots, k_n are chosen such that the roots of the characteristic equation (36) lie on the left half of the S-plane. This placement ensures the system's stability, as poles on the left half of the plane correspond to stable system dynamics.

However, the performance of the controller significantly deteriorates when the system encounters substantial uncertainty, input disturbances, or noisy measurements. In this context, we assume that the functions $f(x)$ and b are unknown, making the ideal controller Equation (31) infeasible. Despite this, the fuzzy IF-THEN rules offer a description of the controller's behavior, enabling an alternative approach to handle the uncertainties.

Thus, rather than directly using the ideal control input u^* , it is reasonable to replace it with a fuzzy control input. This leads to the following formulation:

$$u^* \approx \underline{\theta}^{*T} \underline{\tau}(\underline{x}) \quad (37)$$

In this context, $\underline{\theta}^*$ represents the vector of centroids for the membership functions assigned to the ideal control input u^* , while $\underline{\tau}(\underline{x})$ refers to the vector of fuzzy basis functions.

The control law, as shown in Equation (37), is implemented using an estimate $\underline{\theta}$ of the true value of $\underline{\theta}^*$. Therefore, the control law can be expressed as:

$$u = u_c(\underline{\theta}, \underline{x}) = \underline{\theta}^T \underline{\tau}(\underline{x}) \quad (38)$$

Substituting $u_c(\underline{\theta}, \underline{x})$ in equation (29) leads to:

$$\dot{\underline{x}} = f(\underline{x}) + b u_c(\underline{\theta}, \underline{x}) \quad (39)$$

Adding and subtracting $b u^*$ to equation (39) result in:

$$\dot{\underline{x}} = f(\underline{x}) + b u^* + b (u_c(\underline{\theta}, \underline{x}) - u^*) \quad (40)$$

In a manner similar to the derivation of equation (34), it can be demonstrated that the error model for the closed-loop system described by equation (40) is:

$$\ddot{\underline{e}} = -\underline{k}^T \underline{e} + b (u^* - u_c(\underline{\theta}, \underline{x})) \quad (41)$$

Equation (43) can be expressed in vector form as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{e}_1 &= \dot{e} = e_2, \\ \dot{e}_2 &= \ddot{e} = -\underline{k}^T \underline{e} + b (u^* - u_c(\underline{\theta}, \underline{x})) \end{aligned} \quad (42)$$

So, the state space model takes the form:

$$\dot{\underline{e}} = \Lambda_c \underline{e} + b_c (u^* - u_c(\underline{\theta}, \underline{x})) \quad (43)$$

Where:

$$\Lambda_c = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -k_2 & -k_1 \end{bmatrix}, b_c = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ b \end{bmatrix}$$

The parameters k_1, \dots, k_n are chosen so that the eigenvalues of the system are positioned within a predetermined region on the left-hand side of the s-plane. This placement ensures the system's stability.

The adaptation rule for $\underline{\theta}$ is generally derived using the second method of Lyapunov, which is a common approach to guarantee the stability of the adaptive system. To demonstrate this, we consider the following Lyapunov function:

$$V = \frac{1}{2} \underline{e}^T P \underline{e} + \frac{b}{2} \underline{\varphi}^T \Gamma^{-1} \underline{\varphi} \quad (44)$$

In this context, P and Γ are matrices that are positive definite, meaning all their eigenvalues are positive, which ensures that they contribute to the stability of the system. The term $\varphi = \underline{\theta}^* - \underline{\theta}$ represents the estimation error, which measures the difference between the estimated and actual values. The specific formulas for computing P and Γ are provided below. The time derivative of V is:

$$\dot{V} = \frac{1}{2}(\underline{e}^T P \underline{e} + \underline{e}^T P \underline{e}) + b \underline{\varphi}^T \Gamma^{-1} \dot{\underline{\varphi}} \quad (45)$$

Substituting for \underline{e} from equation (45) in equation (47) leads to:

$$\dot{V} = \frac{1}{2} \underline{e}^T (P \Lambda_c + \Lambda_c^T P) \underline{e} + \underline{\varphi}^T \tau(\underline{x}) b_c^T P \underline{e} + b_c \underline{\varphi}^T \Gamma^{-1} \dot{\underline{\varphi}} \quad (46)$$

The closed-loop system represented in Equation (43) will be stable if the derivative of V , denoted as V' , is negative semi-definite. Given that the eigenvalues of P are stable, it follows that P satisfies the algebraic Lyapunov equation, which is given as:

$$P \Lambda_c + \Lambda_c^T P = -Q \quad (47)$$

In this case, Q is a positive semi-definite matrix, which means that all its eigenvalues are non-negative, and it is chosen by the designer based on the specific needs of the system. The adaptation law is then selected as follows:

$$\dot{\underline{\varphi}} = -\frac{1}{b} b_c^T P \underline{e} \Gamma \tau(\underline{x}) \quad (48)$$

Hence, it is possible to rewrite equation (47) as:

$$\dot{V} = -\frac{1}{2} \underline{e}^T Q \underline{e} \quad (49)$$

Equation (49) clearly shows that the closed-loop system Equation (43) is stable if the adaptation law equation (48) is employed. To implement equation (48) and calculate $\underline{\theta}$, it is assumed that the variation of $\underline{\theta}^*$ is much slower than that of $\underline{\theta}$, i.e. $\underline{\theta}^*$ is locally constant [28]. The estimation of $\underline{\theta}$ is given by:

$$\dot{\underline{\theta}} = \frac{1}{b} b_c^T P \underline{e} \Gamma \tau(\underline{x}) \quad (50)$$

The adaptation gain Γ as a diagonal matrix is selected by the designer, with γ_i as the i^{th} diagonal element. Due to the unique structure of the vector, the product simplifies to $b p_2$, where p_2 is the 2th row of P ; and the adaptation law in (50) is simplified to:

$$\dot{\theta}_i = \gamma_i \underline{e}^T p_n \tau_i(\underline{x}) \quad (51)$$

Equation (51), which describes the adaptation law, has some limitations due to the use of a pure integrator. To enhance the performance of the estimator, methods like the projection algorithm and sigma-modification have been applied. The estimator in [29] is implemented using a variable structure algorithm, which ensures robust performance and efficient numerical execution. As a result, the formulation of the estimator is given by:

$$\theta_i = \bar{\theta}_i \text{sat} \left(\underline{e}^T p_n \right) + \theta_i(0) \quad (52)$$

Where: $\overline{\theta}_i$ is a constant determined by the designer to define the allowable variation of θ_i around its initial value $\theta_i(0)$.

Results and Discussion

Simulation Results

The proposed control strategy is validated through detailed simulations performed in MATLAB/Simulink. The system parameters utilized for the simulation are outlined in Table 2. The performance of the proposed inverter-side controller is thoroughly analyzed under two key operating scenarios: the worst-case condition (rectifying mode) and inverting mode.

In the rectifying mode, an 800 W load is connected to the DC-link capacitor, while power is supplied by a 3.5 kW PV array. The PV array is composed of 12 series-connected modules, with the parameters for each module specified in Table 3. The controller is implemented in discrete time using an emulation approach with a carefully chosen sampling time to ensure precise digital control. The control parameters, including gains and time constants, are listed in Table 4, while the initial conditions and configurations for the AFLC are detailed in Table 5.

Figure 11 demonstrates the stability of the DLVC loop in both rectifying and inverting modes when the PI regulator is utilized. The results confirm that the voltage loop maintains stability under all tested operating conditions, ensuring reliable system performance.

The PLL compensator, an integral part of the control system, is evaluated for its ability to synchronize with the grid. As illustrated in Figure 12, the PLL rapidly converges to the actual grid angle, achieving synchronization in less than one grid cycle. This fast and accurate convergence is essential for maintaining grid compatibility and ensuring precise control of power flow.

Figure 13 provides a comparative analysis of the dynamic performance of the DC-link voltage controller when employing the PI regulator, FLC, and AFLC in rectifying mode. Initially, the load is disconnected, and the vdc is set to 305 V. The controller then regulates vdc to 380 V. At 0.6 seconds, a load disturbance is introduced, transitioning the system from no-load to full-load conditions.

The figure reveals clear differences in controller performance during transient and steady-state conditions. The AFLC demonstrates superior performance, achieving lower overshoot and faster settling time compared to both the FLC and PI controller. These advantages highlight the AFLC's ability to adapt dynamically to changes in operating conditions, ensuring precise and efficient regulation of the DLV.

Table 2. Converter parameters.

P_{load}	F_{sw}	r_s	L_s	C_{dc}	P_{pv}
800	10	0.1Ω	5	3300	3.5Kw
W	KHz		mH	μF	

Table 3. TSM-295 PC14 PV module characteristics.

Electrical Characteristics	Value
Open circuit voltage ($v_{o.c}$)	45.2 V
Short circuit current ($i_{s.c}$)	8.55 A
PV voltage at MPP (v_{mpp})	36.6 V
PV current at MPP (i_{mpp})	8.07 A
PV power at MPP(p_{mpp})	295 W

Figures 14 and 15 illustrate that the direct-axis grid current i_{gd} accurately tracks the reference signal generated by the DLV controller. Meanwhile, the quadrature-axis grid current i_{gq} is maintained at zero, ensuring no reactive power is injected into or absorbed from the grid. This performance highlights the controller's capability to maintain active power transfer while preventing unwanted reactive power interaction.

In the inverting mode, the current controller is further assessed under various conditions. Initially, a square wave reference signal alternating between 5 A and 10 A is applied to i_{gdref} , while i_{gqref} is kept at 0 A. As depicted in Figure 16, both i_{gd} and i_{gq} exhibit accurate tracking of their respective reference signals. This precise tracking ensures the injected power adheres to the required standards, as further confirmed in Figures 17 and 18.

The system's response is further analyzed under varying power injection conditions. Figure 19 presents the measured i_{gd} and i_{gq} when P_{gref} is set to 800 W, and Q_{gref} is adjusted from 0 to 400 VAR. The corresponding active and reactive power injected into the grid are illustrated in Figure 20. These results demonstrate that the system effectively delivers the specified power levels, maintaining operational stability.

Finally, the phase relationship between the grid current and voltage is examined under different power injection scenarios. Figure 21 shows that when $(P_{gref}, Q_{gref}) = (800 \text{ W}, 0)$, the grid current remains in phase with the grid voltage, ensuring optimal active power transfer. Conversely, when $(P_{gref}, Q_{gref}) = (800 \text{ W}, 400 \text{ VAR})$, the grid current lags the grid voltage, indicating reactive power injection. This behavior underscores the flexibility and reliability of the controller in managing active and reactive power delivery.

To evaluate the dynamic performance of the DLV controller operating in inverting mode, a step-change reference signal alternating between 460 V and 390 V is applied. This test is designed to assess the controller's ability to respond to rapid changes in the DLV reference while maintaining stability and accuracy.

Figure 22 highlights the exceptional performance of the AFLC under these conditions. The AFLC exhibits a fast dynamic response, ensuring that the DLV quickly reaches the new reference value following each step change. Additionally, the controller minimizes overshoot, preventing excessive deviations above the target voltage during transient conditions. This characteristic is critical in preventing stress on the power electronic components and maintaining overall system reliability.

Moreover, the AFLC achieves a small steady-state error, maintaining the DLV close to the desired reference value once the transient response has settled. This precision in steady-state operation ensures efficient power transfer and optimal system performance. These results confirm that the AFLC is well-suited for dynamic scenarios, providing robust control of the DC-link voltage in inverting mode while adhering to stringent performance criteria.

Table 4. Control parameters.

k_e	$k_{\Delta e}$	$k_{\Delta idref}$	$\bar{\theta}$	k_p	k_{il}	k_{pi}	k_{ii}	k_{pv}	k_{iv}
0.01	3	-0.1	-0.5	2.57	2730.3 S ⁻¹	30	620 S ⁻¹	0.36	21.2 S ⁻¹

Table 5. Initial rules of the AFLC.

Δe \ e	N	Z	P
N	1	1	0
Z	1	0	-1
P	0	-1	-1

Figure 11. Bode plot of compensated of the DLV loop using PI-controller.

Fig. 12. Grid angle detection using PLL.

Figure 13. vdc response using PI-controller, FLC and AFLC in rectifying mode.

Figure 14. The dynamic response of i_{gd} and i_{gq} in rectifying mode.

Figure 15. v_g and i_g in rectifying mode.

Figure 16. The dynamic response of i_{gd} and i_{gq} at step change of i_{gdref} (from 5 A to 10 A) at unity power factor

Figure 17. v_g and i_g at step change of i_{gdref} (from 5 A to 10 A) at unity power factor.

Figure 18. Harmonic spectrum of i_g .

Figure 19. i_{gd} and i_{gq} at P_{gref} is set to 800 W and Q_{gref} is changed from zero to 400VAR.

Figure 20. The injected power when P_{gref} is set to 800 W and Q_{gref} is changed from zero to 400VAR.

Figure 21. v_g and i_g at P_{gref} is set to 800 W and Q_{gref} is changed from zero to 400VAR.

Figure 22. The dynamic response of V_{dc} using a PI-controller, FLC and AFLC in inverting mode.

Experimental Results

The inverter-side controller is subjected to experimental testing under the worst-case operating condition, specifically in rectifying mode, by connecting an 800-watt load to the DC bus. This scenario is designed to evaluate the robustness and performance of the controller under high-stress conditions. Figures 23 and 24 provide a detailed illustration of the schematic circuit and the experimental setup used for testing in rectifying mode.

The V_{dc} is regulated using three different controllers: a PI controller, a FLC, and an AFLC. The dynamic performance of these controllers is compared based on critical metrics, including maximum overshoot and steady-state error, to determine their effectiveness in maintaining the desired DLV.

Figure 25 demonstrates the response of the controlled V_{dc} for the PI controller, FLC, and AFLC under an identical sequence of events. Initially, the load is disconnected, the enable pulse to the controller is blocked, and all controllers are inactive. During this phase, the DC-link capacitor charges to approximately 305 V through the anti-parallel diodes of the VSI. Once the initial charging phase is complete, the V_{dcref} is adjusted from 305 V to 380 V at a rate of 75 V/s. After the DLV stabilizes at 380 V, a load disturbance is introduced by transitioning from no load to full load.

The comparison of the responses clearly indicates significant differences in the performance of the three controllers. Both the FLC and AFLC demonstrate superior tracking performance, with the measured V_{dc} showing zero steady-state deviation from the reference value. This indicates their ability to accurately

regulate the DLV under both transient and steady-state conditions. In contrast, the PI controller exhibits a slower dynamic response and noticeable deviations during load disturbances.

Furthermore, the AFLC outperforms the FLC in terms of transient behavior. The AFLC achieves a lower overshoot during the voltage transition and reaches the steady-state value more rapidly compared to the FLC. This enhanced performance highlights the AFLC's ability to combine the advantages of adaptive tuning and fuzzy logic, making it highly effective for dynamic voltage regulation under varying load conditions. These results emphasize the AFLC's suitability for applications requiring high precision and fast response in rectifying mode operations.

Figure 23. Schematic circuit in rectifying mode.

Figure 24. The experimental bench in rectifying mode.

Figure 25. Experimental results for the transient response of DLVC loop PI, FLC and AFLC in rectifying mode.

Figure 26 illustrates the experimental setup of the single-stage system, which includes a PV array, a VSI, a filter inductor, a grid, driving and interfacing circuits, and a dSPACE controller box. This system is designed for evaluation purposes within a laboratory setting at ERI, as depicted in figure 27. During this test, the MPPT block is temporarily disabled, and a stepping reference voltage v_{dc_ref} is used to control the DLV loop, alternating between 460 V and 390 V. Experimental results depicting the transient response of DLVC action in inverting mode are shown in Figure 28 for the PI controller, FLC, and AFLC. The figure confirms the superior performance of the AFLC in terms of rapid dynamic response, minimal overshoot, and low steady-state error, aligning with the expected results from the simulations.

Figure 26. Circuit diagram of a single-stage, single-phase grid-connected PV system.

Figure 27. Overview of the experimental setup.

Figure 28. Analysis of DLV Behavior in the Inverting Mode Using PI, FLC, and Adaptive FLC Controllers.

Conclusion

This study introduces a complete design for the control unit of a single-phase H-bridge inverter, specifically tailored for operation within the DQ reference frame. The proposed control strategy is structured around two fundamental control loops: the first loop focuses on maintaining the stability of the DLV, while the second loop ensures precise regulation of the output current. Together, these loops enable efficient and reliable integration of the inverter with the power grid.

To optimize the power flow injected into the grid, a PI controller is employed, offering robust performance in tracking and regulating grid power injection. Additionally, the control framework incorporates a DC-bus voltage compensator, which is designed and evaluated using three distinct control methodologies: a PI controller, a FLC, and an AFLC. This multifaceted approach allows for a comparative analysis of the controllers, highlighting their respective advantages in terms of stability, dynamic response, and adaptability to changing operating conditions. By integrating these control techniques, the study

demonstrates the potential for improved performance and reliability of grid-tied single-phase inverters, making a significant contribution to the field of renewable energy integration and smart grid technology.

The dynamic response of the DLV is evaluated in both rectifying and inverting modes under no-load conditions and then under full-load conditions. The results indicate that the AFLC mitigates disturbances 0.2 seconds faster than the FLC, achieving zero steady-state error in rectifying mode. In inverting mode, the DLV exhibits critically damped behavior when using the AFLC. The experimental results reveal that the PI controller, without a feed-forward signal from the DC side, is ineffective at rejecting disturbances, adversely impacting its performance in both rectifying and inverting modes. The active and reactive power injected into or absorbed from the grid is controlled in the DQ frame using a PI controller. The results demonstrate that the current injected into or absorbed from the grid maintains high quality with low total harmonic distortion, meeting the requirements for distributed generators.

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